

A multi-group analytical model for the kinetic parameters

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ABSTRACT

In the framework of the Verification&Validation activities conducted by *newcleo* for its Lead-cooled Fast Reactor design tools, this work presents an analytical derivation of reactor kinetic parameters within the multi-group diffusion theory for homogeneous systems. Explicit expressions for the forward and adjoint fluxes are obtained, enabling closed-form evaluations of β_{eff} and Λ_{eff} . The proposed model provides physical insight into the group-wise contribution of kinetic parameters and serves as a reference for verifying numerical codes. Despite its simplifying assumptions, it offers valuable benchmarks for liquid-metal fast reactors and paves the way for future extensions including finer group structures, analytical sensitivities, and up-scattering effects.

Keywords: kinetic parameters, analytical solution, effective delayed neutron fraction, effective mean generation time

1. INTRODUCTION

newcleo is currently performing an extensive Verification&Validation campaign for qualifying the scientific computing tools adopted in the design calculations of its Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR) units, including the evaluation of the kinetic parameters. These integral quantities are fundamental to assess the kinetic features of the systems under design and to perform safety studies using the point kinetics model.

In this framework, regulatory guidance emphasizes the importance of both a thorough understanding of the physical phenomena involved and the use of reference solutions when available. In particular, the Guide n.28 of the French Nuclear Safety Authority [1] underlines that the validation of computational tools should rely on experimental measurements and, whenever possible, on analytical benchmarks. Furthermore, the same guide stresses the necessity of identifying and hierarchizing the dominant physical phenomena in the application domain, as well as of ensuring that numerical codes are capable of reproducing them with adequate accuracy.

Within this context, analytical models represent a valuable complement to numerical simulations, providing physical insights and yielding reproducible benchmarks that can be used to verify and increase confidence in more complex tools. In reactor kinetics, closed-form solutions are particularly relevant because they enable the explicit link between fundamental physical assumptions and the resulting integral parameters, thereby clarifying the role of approximations and limiting cases.

The present work contributes to this effort by deriving analytical expressions for the kinetic parameters within the framework of multi-group diffusion theory, assuming a spatially homogeneous system treated in the space-asymptotic approximation. The resulting closed-form solutions for the forward and adjoint fluxes provide a reference analytical model for verifying the capability of numerical codes to evaluate adjoint fluxes and the associated kinetic parameters. While analytical benchmarks are available

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for two-group diffusion models and a few studies have addressed three-group formulations [2], explicit multi-group closed-form results for kinetic parameters remain scarce. Building on the analytical development presented in [3] for the time-eigenvalue problem, the present formulation extends the approach to derive group-wise expressions for both the forward and adjoint fluxes, enabling a consistent evaluation of the kinetic parameters. This is particularly relevant in the context of Verification&Validation given the limited availability of experimental data - especially for Λ_{eff} . Finally, illustrative calculations are presented for liquid-metal fast reactor configurations.

2. ANALYTICAL DERIVATION

In this section, we derive the analytical expressions of the kinetic parameters in a multi-group space-asymptotic framework [4]. Consistently with the physical evidence, we assume that fission neutrons cannot be emitted in the thermal range, hence χ vanishes below a certain threshold group h , i.e. $\chi_g = 0 \forall g \geq h$. In this paper, we also assume that up-scattering is negligible, i.e. $\Sigma_{g \rightarrow g'} = 0$ when $g > g'$, even though it might be relevant in the thermal energy range for both fast and thermal systems [5, 6].

Considering a spatially homogenised system, the direct and adjoint space-asymptotic (i.e., diffusion) models can be cast as algebraic equations, respectively

$$D_g B^2 \phi_g + \Sigma_{r,g} \phi_g - \sum_{\substack{g'=1 \\ g' \neq g}}^G \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{g'} = \frac{1}{k} \chi_g \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'}, \quad g = 1, \dots, G \quad (1)$$

and

$$D_g B^2 \phi_g^\dagger + \Sigma_{r,g} \phi_g^\dagger - \sum_{\substack{g'=1 \\ g' \neq g}}^G \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow g'} \phi_{g'}^\dagger = \frac{1}{k} \nu \Sigma_{f,g} \sum_{g'=1}^G \chi_{g'} \phi_{g'}^\dagger, \quad g = 1, \dots, G. \quad (2)$$

The symbols have their usual meaning as it can be found in classical books [7]. Following the formalism presented in [3], the k -eigenvalue can be expressed as a sum of contributions over each possible "multiplication path" p followed by a neutron from its emission group g_0 to its multiplication group g_f :

$$k = \sum_p k_p = \sum_{g_0=1}^G \chi_{g_0} \sum_{g_f=g_0}^G \sum_{p \in \{g_0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow g_f\}} \left[\prod_{(g \rightarrow g') \in p} P_{s,g \rightarrow g'} \right] \nu_{g_f} P_{f,g_f}, \quad (3)$$

where the P -terms can be interpreted as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{NL},g} &= \frac{1}{1 + L_g^2 B^2} = \text{non-leakage probability} \\ P_{s,g \rightarrow g'} &= \frac{\Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow g'}}{\Sigma_{r,g}} P_{\text{NL},g} = \text{scattering probability from } g \text{ to } g' \\ P_{f,g} &= \frac{\Sigma_{f,g}}{\Sigma_{r,g}} P_{\text{NL},g} = \text{fission probability.} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For example, in a 3-group model we obtain (assuming $\chi_3 = 0$):

$$\begin{aligned} k &= \chi_1 (\nu_1 P_{f,1} + P_{s,1 \rightarrow 2} \nu_2 P_{f,2} + P_{s,1 \rightarrow 3} \nu_3 P_{f,3} + P_{s,1 \rightarrow 2} P_{s,2 \rightarrow 3} \nu_3 P_{f,3}) + \chi_2 (\nu_2 P_{f,2} + P_{s,2 \rightarrow 3} \nu_3 P_{f,3}) = \\ &= k_1 + k_{1 \rightarrow 2} + k_{1 \rightarrow 3} + k_{1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3} + k_2 + k_{2 \rightarrow 3}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where, for instance, the path $(1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3)$ indicates that a neutron is emitted in 1, it slows down in group 2 and then in 3, where it finally does fission. Even though Equation (3) allows to estimate

the contribution of each path to the reactivity, its direct application may become prohibitive in practice when G is large, since the number of possible paths explodes. At the price of a small loss of information, but not physical accuracy, a practical workaround consists in summing each k_p sharing the same g_0 and g_f , by introducing the transition probability $P_{g_0 \rightarrow g_f}$ [3],

$$P_{g_0 \rightarrow g_f} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } g_0 = g_f, \\ \sum_{g=g_0}^{g_f-1} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g} P_{s,g \rightarrow g_f} & \text{if } g_0 \neq g_f. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

This approach dramatically reduces the number of calculations and allows to get

$$k_{g_0 \rightarrow g_f} = \chi_{g_0} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g_f} \nu_{g_f} P_{f,g_f} \quad g_0 = 1, \dots, G \quad g_f = 1, \dots, G. \quad (7)$$

The ratio $\sum_{g_0=1}^{g_f} k_{g_0 \rightarrow g_f} / k$ yields the average number of neutrons produced by fission in g_f due to all neutrons born in the other groups, i.e. it coincides with the fission rate in group g_f . Exploiting this evidence and imposing a unitary fission source, namely $\langle 1 | \hat{F} \phi \rangle = 1$, the direct flux can be expressed as

$$\phi_g = \frac{1}{\nu \sum_{f,g}} \frac{\sum_{g_0=1}^g k_{g_0 \rightarrow g}}{k}. \quad (8)$$

For the sake of brevity, we omit the full algebraic derivation. The dual mathematical derivation for the adjoint holds only for those groups where the adjoint fission rate $\chi_g \phi_g^+ > 0$. For the groups where $\chi_g = 0$ ($g \geq h$), it is convenient to solve explicitly for each ϕ_g^+ in the corresponding adjoint diffusion equation. By imposing $\langle \phi^+ | \hat{F} \phi \rangle = 1$ and solving the equations from $g = G$ to $g = h$, we can find a compact and closed expression for ϕ^+ as well,

$$\phi_g^+ = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\chi_g} \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g_0=g}^G k_{g_0 \rightarrow g} & g = 1, \dots, h-1 \\ \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g'=g}^G P_{g \rightarrow g'} \nu_{g'} P_{f,g'} & g = h, \dots, G. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

It should be noticed that the duality between Equation (9) and Equation (8) holds only for $g' \leq h$. When $g \geq h$, $\chi_g = 0$ and the value of ϕ_g^+ is given by all the fissions occurring in $g' \geq g$ due to neutrons departing from g . This is a consequence of the adjoint scattering operators coupling lower-energy fluxes with higher-energy fluxes.

The analytical expressions of the direct and adjoint fluxes allow to retrieve an analytical expression for the kinetic parameters as a sum of group-wise terms. For the effective lifetime, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_{\text{eff}} &= \frac{\langle \phi^+ | \hat{V}^{-1} \phi \rangle}{\langle \phi^+ | \hat{F} \phi \rangle} = \sum_{g=1}^G \phi_g^+ \frac{1}{\nu_g} \phi_g = \sum_{g=1}^{h-1} \frac{1}{\nu_g} \phi_g \phi_g^+ + \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{1}{\nu_g} \phi_g \phi_g^+ \\ &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=1}^{h-1} \frac{1}{\nu_g} \frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{1}{\chi_g \nu \sum_{f,g}} \sum_{g_0=1}^g k_{g_0 \rightarrow g} \sum_{g_f=g}^G k_{g \rightarrow g_f} \right) + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{1}{\nu_g} \frac{\phi_g^+}{\nu \sum_{f,g}} \sum_{g_0=1}^g k_{g_0 \rightarrow g}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The first term can be manipulated recalling Equation (7),

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{g=1}^{h-1} \frac{1}{v_g} \phi_g \phi_g^\dagger &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=1}^{h-1} \frac{1}{v_g} \frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{1}{\chi_g v \Sigma_{f,g}} \sum_{g_0=1}^g \chi_{g_0} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g} v_g P_{f,g} \sum_{g_f=g}^G \chi_{g_f} P_{g \rightarrow g_f} v_{g_f} P_{f,g_f} \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=1}^{h-1} \frac{1}{v_g} \frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{\chi_g v_g P_{f,g}}{\chi_g v \Sigma_{f,g}} \sum_{g_0=1}^g \chi_{g_0} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g} \sum_{g_f=g}^G P_{g \rightarrow g_f} v_{g_f} P_{f,g_f} \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=1}^{h-1} \frac{1}{k} \frac{P_{NL,g}}{\Sigma_{r,g} v_g} \left(\sum_{g_0=1}^g \chi_{g_0} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g} \sum_{g_f=g}^G P_{g \rightarrow g_f} v_{g_f} P_{f,g_f} \right) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=1}^{h-1} \frac{\ell_g}{k} \sum_{g \in p} k_p,
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

while the second one reads

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{1}{v_g} \phi_g \phi_g^\dagger &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\phi_g^\dagger}{v \Sigma_{f,g}} \sum_{g_0=1}^g k_{g_0 \rightarrow g} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\phi_g^\dagger}{v \Sigma_{f,g}} \sum_{g_0=1}^g \chi_{g_0} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g} v_g P_{f,g} \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{P_{NL,g}}{\Sigma_{r,g} v_g} \sum_{g_0=1}^g \chi_{g_0} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g} \phi_g^\dagger = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{\ell_g}{k} \sum_{g_0=1}^g \chi_{g_0} P_{g_0 \rightarrow g} \sum_{g_f=g}^G P_{g \rightarrow g_f} v_{g_f} P_{f,g_f} \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g=h}^G \frac{\ell_g}{k} \sum_{g \in p} k_p.
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

In both cases, the sum over k_p involves any path transiting for the group g . These two equations allow to express the effective lifetime as a weighted sum of the group-wise neutron effective lifetimes,

$$\Lambda_{\text{eff}} = \sum_{g=1}^G \frac{\ell_g}{k} \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g \in p} k_p = \sum_{g=1}^G \frac{\ell_g}{k} w_{g,\Lambda_{\text{eff}}} = \sum_{g=1}^G \Lambda_{\text{eff},g} w_{g,\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}. \tag{13}$$

The weight $w_{g,\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ represents the contribution to k of the neutrons whose multiplication path p involves a transition in group g . For instance, when $G = 3$, Equation (13) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Lambda_{\text{eff}} &= \frac{\ell_1}{k} \frac{(k_1 + k_{1 \rightarrow 2} + k_{1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3} + k_{1 \rightarrow 3})}{k} + \frac{\ell_2}{k} \frac{(k_2 + k_{2 \rightarrow 3} + k_{1 \rightarrow 2} + k_{1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3})}{k} + \\
 &+ \frac{\ell_3}{k} \frac{(k_{1 \rightarrow 3} + k_{2 \rightarrow 3} + k_{1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3})}{k}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

In addition to its clear physical interpretation, Equation (13) allows to explicitly determine the contribution of each group to Λ_{eff} , which may be relevant in a set of different applications, e.g., sensitivity and uncertainty analyses. However, the estimation of the different k_p terms to compute $w_{g,\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ may become too expensive for relatively small values of G . A more practical alternative consists in using the flux and the adjoint,

$$w_{g,\Lambda_{\text{eff}}} = \frac{k}{\ell_g} \frac{\phi_g^\dagger \phi_g}{v_g}. \tag{15}$$

The analytical expression for the effective delayed neutron fraction yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 \beta_{\text{eff},i} &= \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger | \hat{F}_{d,i} \phi \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger | \hat{F} \phi \rangle} = \langle \phi^\dagger | \hat{F}_{d,i} \phi \rangle = \beta_i \sum_{g=1}^G \phi_g^\dagger \chi_{d,i,g} \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'} = \\
 &= \beta_i \sum_{g=1}^G \phi_g^\dagger \chi_{d,i,g} = \beta_i \sum_{g=1}^G \frac{\chi_{d,i,g}}{\chi_g} \frac{1}{k} \sum_{g_0=1}^G k_{g \rightarrow g_0} \\
 &= \beta_i \sum_{g=1}^G \frac{\chi_{d,i,g}}{\chi_g} w_{g,\beta_{\text{eff}}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Thanks to the choice of the normalisation adopted, the "effectiveness" factor applied to the physical β to construct β_{eff} is simply the sum over each group of the delayed emission spectrum weighted by the adjoint flux in the same group. In this analytical framework, the effectiveness factor featuring group g is given by the overall number of descendant neutrons (*progeny*) produced due to a single delayed neutron (*ancestor*) emitted in g , consistently with the Iterated Fission Probability interpretation [8]. For instance, in the three-group case (assuming $\chi_3 = 0$), the following equation is obtained,

$$\beta_{\text{eff},i} = \beta_i \left(\frac{\chi_{d,i,1}}{\chi_1} (k_1 + k_{1 \rightarrow 2} + k_{1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3} + k_{1 \rightarrow 3}) + \frac{\chi_{d,i,2}}{\chi_2} (k_2 + k_{2 \rightarrow 3}) \right). \tag{17}$$

3. RESULTS

In this section we show an application of the analytical solutions presented in the paper, focused on four reactor configurations with the same cylindrical geometry (radius 210 cm, height 350 cm): MOX- and UOX-fuelled versions of both Lead- and Sodium-cooled Fast Reactors (LFR and SFR, respectively). The group constants characterising each reactor are scored with the OpenMC code [9] on the ECCO-33 energy group structure. All analytical results obtained in the paper were verified, whenever possible, against numerical calculations produced solving Equation (1) and Equation (2) with the standard `eigs` solver available in the SciPy library.

Figure 1 shows the matrix obtained considering each $k_{g_0 \rightarrow g_f}$ contribution to the multiplication eigenvalue k . Since $k_{g_0 \rightarrow g_f}$ collects any possible path p joining the emission group g_0 and the group g_f where the neutrons do fission, these figures give interesting insights related to the multiplication process in the different reactors. Except for minor differences related to the resonances of Na and Pb (e.g. the depression in $g_f = 18$ for Na^{23}), the most striking difference in the maps is related, as expected, to the fuel choice. MOX-fuelled systems have a narrower multiplication window compared to UOX-fuelled systems, where fission in the low epithermal regions plays an important role.

The direct and adjoint spectra featuring the four systems, displayed in Figure 2, offer new aspects to interpret the multiplication maps in Figure 1. While the profile of the neutron spectra is qualitatively similar in all systems, the neutron importance is very sensitive to the fuel composition. In MOX systems, the adjoint is proportional to the neutron energy [10], while in UOX-fuelled reactors also neutrons at lower energies are important, thus explaining the different "multiplication windows" observed previously.

Building on these observation, it is possible to get some insights in the different values of the kinetic parameters for the four systems, reported in Table I. MOX-fuelled systems featured a much shorter Λ_{eff} than UOX-fuelled systems, while the impact of the coolant is much smaller. Despite the lifetime ℓ being quite similar for all systems, except some minor differences related to the coolant (see Figure 3), the group-wise weights $w_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ are quite different according to the fuel composition. In UOX systems, Λ_{eff} is larger as a consequence of the non-negligible k_p contributions in the thermal groups, where the neutron

Figure 1. Contributions to k due to all k_p sharing the same emission group g_0 and the same multiplication group g_f for the four systems analysed. The grey squares are values falling below the threshold 10^{-2} .

Figure 2. Direct (left) and adjoint (right) spectra featuring the four homogeneous systems analysed.

lifetime is maximum. Conversely, the number of thermal fissions in MOX-fuelled systems is negligible, shortening the effective lifetime.

Following a similar approach, Figure 4 shows the decomposition of the terms in Equation (16) with respect to the energy. To enable the comparison on the same graph, all weights are normalised to unity, while the ratio χ_d/χ_t is graphed against the right axis. Since $w_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}$ mostly shows the same trend for all reactors, the magnitude of β_{eff} is mostly determined by the delayed-to-total spectrum ratio of the emission.

	β_{eff} [pcm]	Λ_{eff} [μs]
LFR-MOX	308	0.943
SFR-MOX	312	1.191
LFR-UOX	561	40.543
SFR-UOX	520	40

Table I. Kinetic parameters of the systems analysed.

Figure 3. Weights $w_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ (left), effective lifetime ℓ (middle) and effective prompt lifetime Λ_{eff} (right) as a function of the energy.

Figure 4. Weights $w_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}$, χ_d/χ ratio and β_{eff} as a function of the energy.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents a multi-group analytical framework for the derivation of the main integral parameters in a reactor, with a special focus on the kinetic parameters. Despite the clear limitations due to the simplifying assumptions introduced, the simple model presented in this paper provides an intuitive physical interpretation of the kinetic parameters, naturally decomposing them in group-wise contributions and offering a reference solution for benchmarking numerical codes as well as sensitivity and uncertainty calculations. The results obtained allows to get important insight regarding the kinetic parameters obtained considering different combinations of fuel and coolant in liquid-metal fast reactors, offering a support for their design.

Future work will focus on a comparison between an analytical fine-group calculation and reference experimental results available (e.g., the Godiva and Jezebel critical spheres) in order to estimate the impact of the simplifying assumptions on the model accuracy. Another interesting future development of the work could be related to Sensitivity and Uncertainty applications, which could leverage on the analytical expressions of the group-wise contribution to the kinetic parameters for deriving analytical sensitivity profiles for code verification.

Another important although challenging task that could be addressed in the future is the extension of the model to include also the up-scattering phenomenon - which may be non-negligible in fast reactors when using fine-group structures - to possibly yield a more precise estimate of the kinetic parameters, especially for Λ_{eff} .

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